

Assessing the Relevance of the Normative Theory of the Press in Contemporary Nigerian Media

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Abstract

This paper examines the relevance of the Normative Theory of the Press in contemporary Nigerian media, focusing on the balance between press freedom, social responsibility, and developmental objectives. The Normative Theory, which categorizes press systems into models such as the authoritarian, libertarian, social responsibility, and Soviet-communist frameworks, provides a conceptual lens for evaluating how media institutions operate within political, economic, and cultural contexts. In Nigeria, the media landscape has evolved from a state-controlled press to a dynamic, pluralistic environment characterized by private ownership, digital innovation, and a proliferation of social media platforms. The study explores how Nigerian journalists and media organizations negotiate the tension between exercising freedom of expression and fulfilling societal obligations, including promoting democracy, public accountability, and national development. It highlights the challenges posed by political interference, economic pressures, ethical lapses, and the rise of misinformation, which test the applicability of traditional normative frameworks. Drawing on recent media practices and regulatory policies as well as existing literature, the paper argues that while the Normative Theory of the Press remains a valuable analytical tool, its relevance in Nigeria requires adaptation to contemporary realities, particularly in the digital era where media influence extends beyond conventional print and broadcast platforms. The analysis contributes to scholarly debates on media ethics, governance, and development communication by demonstrating that normative principles must be contextually interpreted to guide responsible journalism in a rapidly changing Nigerian media environment.

Keywords

Assessing; Contemporary; Media; Normative Theories and Relevance

I. Introduction

Normative theories of the press occupy a central place in mass communication because they provide value-oriented frameworks for understanding how the media ought to function in society. Unlike descriptive or empirical media theories, which focus on explaining how media systems operate in practice, normative theories are obviously prescriptive. They explain the moral precepts, professional norms, and social expectations that govern media behavior in particular political, social, and economic situations (McQuail, 2015). Normative media theory is predicated on the idea that the media is not an isolated entity; rather, the dominant values, power dynamics, and institutional structures of the societies in which media institutions are embedded both impact and are impacted by them. Thus, normative theories highlight the mutual connection between media systems and their social environment, highlighting the media's responsibility to serve the public interest while remaining accountable to societal norms and democratic ideals (Christians et al., 2019).

Different political philosophies, cultural norms, economic structures, governing frameworks, and historical experiences all contribute to cultural diversity in media systems. Therefore, normative theories emphasize the relationship between the press, the

government, and the people in an effort to explain media behaviours by connecting them to larger societal realities. Normative theory of the press consists of philosophical concepts, value judgments, prescribed media roles, ethical norms, and regulatory expectations that outline how the media should operate in society (Vitalis et al., 2025).

In order to explain how the press should operate under various social and political conditions, scholars like Siebert, Peterson, and Schramm, as well as later contributors like Dennis McQuail, developed foundational normative frameworks. These frameworks included the authoritarian, libertarian, social responsibility, Soviet-communist, development media theory, and democratic-participant theories. These theories were developed during a period when communication environments were dominated by traditional mass media (Vitalis et al., 2023). It is becoming more and more necessary to reevaluate the presumptions underlying traditional normative theories in light of the significant global shifts in political institutions, leadership philosophies, and communication technologies, especially in the post-Cold War and digital eras (Aondover et al., 2025).

While numerous revisions and alternative models have been proposed—sometimes through mere nomenclatural adjustments or abstract theoretical extensions—the original four normative theories remain dominant in media studies. This persistence calls into doubt the applicability of these theories to the explanation of modern media realities, particularly in countries that are pluralistic, globalized, and digitally networked (Aondover et al., 2024). Thus, this study looks at the fundamental ideas of normative media theories, the critics and reviews, the theoretical frameworks, and how they apply to the society, the media, and the government.

1.1 Normative Theories of the Press: Classical Roots and Digital-era Critiques

McQuail criticizes the traditional Four Theories of the Press for being too idealized and Western-centric, with little relevance to diverse and modern media systems, even while he recognizes the need for normative theories in directing media accountability. This criticism emphasizes the necessity for updated normative theories that take into account the realities of digital and non-Western media (Aondover et al., 2022).

The traditional normative theories, Authoritarian, Libertarian, Social Responsibility, and Soviet are constrained, according to McQuail, because they primarily concentrate on political news and information and provide "little of relevance... which might realistically be applied to the cinema, to the music industry, to the video market or even to a good deal of sport, fiction, and entertainment on television, thus to much of what the media are doing most of the time." They defined freedom of the press almost entirely according to interpretations of the U.S. First Amendment, making them overly Western-centric.

However, McQuail (1987) added two further normative models: Democratic-Participant Theory and Development Media Theory because existing normative theories did not adequately explain media roles in non-Western or developing contexts. Beyond McQuail's criticism, academics like Curran (2002) and Nerone (1995) contend that traditional normative theories of the press are historically limited, unduly simplistic, and inadequately aware of economic power, ownership structures, and cultural settings. According to these criticisms, the role of journalism in digital, networked, and platform-dominated media settings cannot be adequately explained by conventional normative frameworks (Castells, 2009; Couldry & Hepp, 2017).

Oluwasola (2020) states that "the philosophical assumptions of some normative media theories require re-examination as new models are needed, given the current social

realities in the wake of the increasingly complex media environment." This point of view reflects a growing consensus that the structure of media systems has been fundamentally altered by the rise of digital platforms, social media, and algorithmic gatekeeping, raising questions about the applicability of normative presumptions from the mid-20th century. Notwithstanding these criticisms, contemporary research also highlights the long-lasting impact of traditional normative ideas in media studies (Onyejelem et al., 2025).

In the words of Oluwasola (2020), "Although revisions done to these theories are either nomenclature changes or additions, the original four normative theories remain dominant in media studies." This suggests that the core ideas of authoritarianism, libertarianism, and social responsibility continue to influence academic discourse, policy discussions, and journalism education even while scholars recognize the need for adaptation.

Baran (2021) provides a comprehensive re-analysis of normative concepts, emphasizing their continued relevance in evaluating media ethics, professionalism, and democratic responsibility. Despite technical developments, the author argues that normative frameworks are crucial to understanding what the media should do rather than just what they do. Austin (2021) expands normative discourse by incorporating racially diverse and inclusive perspectives into communication theory. The work critiques the Western-centric origins of traditional normative theories and calls for contextual reinterpretation to reflect marginalized voices and non-Western media realities. This perspective is particularly useful for analysing African media systems, where cultural values and political structures differ from those of Western democracies.

According to Ogbebor (2020). "Normative theories of the press provide foundations for arguments on how the media can sustain democracy." This perspective holds that normative frameworks serve not just as abstract goals but also as tools for evaluating media performance in relation to democratic aims such as accountability, participation, and public education. This point is particularly crucial in societies where media freedom is contested or administered inconsistently. In contemporary media policy debates, "normative theories relate to expectations from citizens on how the media ought to operate to achieve or maintain prevailing social values" (Ogbebor, 2020; Aondover & Akin-Odukoya, 2024)). This distinction highlights the significance of normative theory in guiding moral values and professional responsibilities, especially in times of political disagreement and misinformation.

Additionally, academics contend that new normative research is required since digital communication technologies have changed how the public, government, and media interact. Digital communication is, nevertheless, "changing media practice, relationships between individuals, media, government, and society," according to the study. Discussions concerning media responsibility, regulation, and the public interest have become more heated as a result of this change, especially when international platforms are starting to play a significant role as public middlemen (Hile et al., 2023). However, normative theories of the press remain significant in media and communication studies because they provide goals for how the media should operate in society.

II. Research Methods

2.1 Theoretical Underpinning

Normative media theory provides a prescriptive framework for understanding how the media ought to operate within different political, social, and economic systems. Rather than describing how media function in practice, normative theory focuses on defining the appropriate roles, freedoms, responsibilities, and ethical obligations of the press in society. It offers evaluative criteria for assessing media performance based on moral principles, democratic values, and societal expectations (McQuail, 2019; Christians et al., 2020).

The framework draws heavily on political philosophy, including liberalism, authoritarianism, socialism, and democratic theory, as well as media ethics and democratic ideals such as the public interest, citizenship, accountability, and the public sphere. A central assumption of normative media theory is that the media exist to serve society and that press freedom must be balanced with responsibility. It further recognizes that the obligations and functions of the media are shaped by the political and socio-economic contexts in which they operate, and that media performance can be assessed using normative and democratic standards rather than purely market-based criteria (Christians et al., 2020).

The theory was developed by three American scholars: Fred S. Siebert, Theodore Peterson, and Wilbur Schramm in 1956, whose classification of press systems provided an early attempt to explain how media should function under different political arrangements. Although their framework has been widely criticized for its conceptual rigidity, Western-centric assumptions, and inability to account for the diversity of contemporary media systems, it remains influential as a reference point in media theory debates (Hallin & Mancini, 2017; McQuail, 2019; Maikaba & Msughter, 2019). Critics argue that the original models oversimplified complex media–state relationships and failed to anticipate global variations and technological change. Nevertheless, elements of these models—particularly the libertarian and social responsibility perspectives—continue to inform analyses of media policy and journalistic practice in liberal democratic contexts (McQuail, 2019).

Building on earlier formulations, succeeding researchers developed and improved normative media theory to accurately depict the realities of postcolonial cultures, participatory communication, and democratic involvement. However, Denis McQuail later amended and expanded it in 1987, adding Democratic-Participant Theory and Development Media Theory. McQuail's updated normative framework incorporates additional theories that emphasize the media's role in grassroots communication, citizen involvement, and national development (McQuail, 2019).

Normative expectations of the media must adapt to different historical, political, and cultural contexts rather than relying on a single universal model. These additions reflect this realization. All things considered, modern normative media theory continues to be a useful analytical framework for assessing media systems, especially in discussions about press freedom, democratic responsibility, media policy, and accountability. Despite adjustments and criticism of its initial formulations, the normative approach provides valuable insights into what the media should do to support democratic life and serve the public interest in an increasingly complex media environment (Christians et al., 2020; Pickard, 2020).

The four press models put out by early researchers are described below, along with the two more models that McQuail introduced. When taken as a whole, these models explain how the press is supposed to function in various political and ideological environments. Different normative presumptions on media accountability, state regulation,

and press freedom are reflected in each paradigm. When taken as a whole, they serve as the cornerstones of normative media theory and offer a useful framework for evaluating journalistic practice and media policy.

2.2 The Authoritarian Theory

The 16th century saw the development of the authoritarian media theory. The media was utilized to support the ruling government during this time, and leadership authority was exerted in a hierarchical or top-down manner. In essence, the media served as the current government's spokesman. The aforementioned conceptual explanations assumed that authoritarian media theory could apply to both contemporary undemocratic or autocratic military systems.

According to this theory, the government has complete control over the media. Through licensing and censorship, the government controls media ownership and operations. According to this idea, the monarch or ruler has divine right and must be obeyed because God has appointed them to serve it. When the concept was implemented under pressure, it violated the right to free expression. High taxation, repressive laws, management of media staff, bans on printing materials, media closures, and the death and imprisonment of journalists under stringent rules were some of the tactics of control used to prevent the press from criticizing the government and its officials. The traces of these controls still exist in third-world countries where the press is controlled by repressive military systems (Daramola, 2003), cited by Elebute (2015). African nations that have had various colonial, military, and autocratic regimes, such as the Gambia, Libya, Egypt, and Nigeria, are prime examples of this theoretical hypothesis.

Also, during the military regimes of Generals Olusegun Obasanjo, Sani Abacha, Ibrahim Babangida, and Muhammadu Buhari/Tunde Idiagbon, essential truths were entrusted to a small group of powerful individuals.

2.3 The Libertarian Theory

According to Siebert et al. (1956), the second prototype of the mainstream first two normative theories is the libertarian media theory, commonly known as the free press, which is most thoroughly developed in the United States of America but applicable elsewhere in the globe. It is the exact opposite of the authoritarian theory. The ideology opposes government meddling in any area of the press and affirms total freedom of public expression and media economic activity. In other words, it encourages free speech and freedom from all types of internal and external restriction. According to the theory, the media should run smoothly, be free from obstacles, and keep the government responsible to the people.

According to John Milton's notion of a free "marketplace of ideas" in the 17th century, a variety of media channels are required to provide a voice to various interests so that citizens can make "informed" decisions using the Libertarian Theory. It will act as a public guardian, monitoring the government to guarantee accountability, transparency, and moral behavior, educating the populace, and preventing power abuse for the greater good. This viewpoint is predicated on an engaged readership whose support or lack thereof, will compel the media to act in the public interest. (Biagi 2014).

The libertarian concept of press freedom has often been described as freedom for publishers to publish whatsoever they wish without any form of responsibility (Curran and Seaton 2010). This point of view is based on the idea that an active readership will compel publishers to act in the public good. (Pickard 2015).

The operations of privately held newspapers and internet media platforms that function without direct government ownership serve as examples of Nigeria's libertarian ideology of the press. Media outlets, including Punch, The Guardian, Vanguard, Premium

Times, and The Cable, frequently look into corruption, critique government policies, and offer forums for a range of political viewpoints. These media outlets practice press freedom by exposing matters of public interest and holding public leaders accountable through investigative stories, editorials, and opinion pieces. For instance, despite pressure from political authorities, investigative journalism like Punch and Premium Times has revealed instances of power abuse, corruption, and poor governance. The libertarian belief that the press should serve as a watchdog over the government and those ideas should be free to flow is reflected in these acts.

However, Section 39(1) of Nigeria's 1999 Constitution, which states that "ownership of the electronic media: radio and television shall be by special license from the president, and staffing shall be controlled by government agents," is a prime example of this direct government control over the media. Nigeria's authoritarian administrations have utilized these media stations to further their goals, even though private investors are still allowed to purchase, establish, and manage media operations.

Additionally, scholars affirm that the libertarian system of governance allows journalists to act excessively and publish stories that they shouldn't. The concept of social responsibility emerged as a result of these critiques.

III. Results and Discussion

3.1 Social Responsibility

The notion of "social responsibility" was initiated by the 1947 Hutchins Commission on freedom of the press in the USA (McQuail 2010, pp. 170–171). The American press was widely criticized for its sensationalism, commercialism, ownership concentration, and suspected abuse of power. As a result, the Commission was established to enforce press accountability (Hartley 2011).

The libertarian idea was modified and the social responsibility theory emerged as a result of the abuse of the freedom from censorship afforded to the media and individuals to publish, own, and run media outlets. In the middle of the 20th century, most developing and third-world nations adopted the social responsibility idea of the press, which was connected to the Hutchins Commission on the Freedom of the Press in the United States in 1942. The concept lies in the middle of authoritarian and libertarian ideologies since it provides total media freedom on the one hand and protection against outside constraints on the other. The fundamental idea of the ideology is that the press must be free while also having an obligation to further the public interest, whether through self-censorship or government regulation.

The liberal theory's social responsibility model, which is in line with the social contract philosophy, contends that the right to obtain and distribute information should be accompanied by a duty to the public, or what academics call "positive freedom" (Pickard 2015). It says that this duty should encompass both the encouragement of public discussions and the portrayal of thorough, accurate, and factual reports. The social responsibility perspective acknowledges a valid role for public or governmental action in media, in contrast to libertarian ideology, which mostly opposes state participation in media matters.

Recent normative media scholarship emphasizes that social responsibility theory does not reject press self-regulation; rather, it regards self-regulation as the preferred means of safeguarding professional standards, editorial independence, and journalistic autonomy. However, when self-regulatory mechanisms prove ineffective or are undermined by commercial pressures, limited intervention by public institutions may be

justified to restore accountability and protect the public interest (Freedman, 2019; Pickard, 2020). This position represents a clear departure from libertarian assumptions that market forces alone are sufficient to ensure media responsibility.

Contemporary analyses by Onyejelem and Aondover (2024a) further demonstrate that the commercial orientation of modern media systems, particularly within liberal democracies, often constrains the press's ability to fulfill its informational and watchdog functions. In such contexts, social responsibility theory supports the involvement of public agencies or policy frameworks to promote pluralism, accuracy, and ethical journalism (Napoli, 2019). Importantly, such interventions are not intended to curtail press freedom but to reinforce democratic communication norms and address structural failures within the media system.

Current scholarship also underscores the enduring influence of social responsibility principles in national and international media policy debates. Studies indicate that these principles continue to inform regulatory discussions, press councils, and public-interest media reforms, especially in response to challenges posed by digital platforms, misinformation, and declining journalistic standards (Couldry & Mejias, 2023; Pickard, 2020). Accordingly, the social responsibility framework advocates measured external intervention when necessary to ensure that the press fulfils its democratic obligations, in contrast to the libertarian model's emphasis on minimal intrusion.

Christians et al. (2020) claim that social democratic media theory emphasizes the need for public policy efforts aimed at addressing market imperfections, promoting pluralism, and ensuring equitable access to information. Despite its normative appeal, social democratic approaches to media regulation have attracted criticism for being overly idealistic or insufficiently explicit in delineating the boundary between legitimate regulation and excessive state interference (Freedman & Goblot, 2018). Nevertheless, recent research suggests that strong professional norms, transparent regulatory frameworks, and institutional safeguards can be established to ensure that statutory involvement strengthens rather than undermines the media's watchdog role in a democracy (Pickard & Williams, 2020).

To ensure that statutory involvement strengthens rather than diminishes the media's watchdog role in a democracy, however, recent research demonstrates that robust professional standards, transparent regulatory frameworks, and institutional protections can be implemented (Pickard & Williams, 2020). Some scholars argue that when media institutions fail to meet their obligations to society—such as providing accurate information, representing diverse viewpoints, and serving the public interest external oversight mechanisms may be justified to safeguard democratic values (McQuail, 2019; Christians et al., 2020).

From this standpoint, press freedom is not conceived as an absolute absence of regulation but as a conditional freedom accompanied by social obligations and ethical responsibilities. Nonetheless, in recent years, counter-hegemonic criticisms of neoliberal press theory have been more well-known. These criticisms contend that commercial pressures, ownership concentration, and a decline in public-interest journalism threaten the media's ability to operate as a democratic institution, challenging the notion that market-driven media systems inherently serve democratic interests (Freedman, 2019; Pickard, 2020).

Even though Section 22 of Chapter 2 of Nigeria's 1999 Constitution mandates that the media monitor the government, hold it responsible to the Nigerian people, and support the state's objectives, the press was not permitted by the constitution to try public officials on the pages of newspapers and magazines, rather they monitor them and hold them

responsible to the people (Elebute 2015). However, regulatory organizations like the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) and the Nigerian Press Council (NPC) oversee media operations in Nigeria, while the Newspapers Proprietors Association of Nigeria (NPAN) and the National Union of Journalism (NUJ) were established to serve as censors of unethical media practices.

3.2 Soviet Communist Theory

The Soviet Communist theory of the press, which was dominant in the former Soviet Union, evolved as a derivative of authoritarian media theory and was rooted in Marxist–Leninist ideology, particularly following the 1917 Russian Revolution. This theory, which represented a more extreme form of authoritarianism, completely subordinated the media to the goals and interests of the state. The ownership, management, and control of the media by the ruling Communist Party ensured strict adherence to Marxist-Leninist doctrine, so it is referred to as the Marxist theory of the press.

According to this ideology, media resources were owned collectively and served mainly as tools to further the political and ideological goals of the party. The press was specifically required to uphold the Communist Party's claim to speak for the interests of the working class, legitimate state power, and advance the socialist system. As a result, the media was seen as an extension of the governmental machinery rather than as a separate organization. Only the state and officially sanctioned socialist party members had access to the media; opposing or nonconformist voices were shut out. Within this framework, public support for social growth and political reform in accordance with the objectives and directions of the Communist Party was largely mobilized through the media.

Because of their widespread use of state repression, communist governments have often been characterized by academics as authoritarian or totalitarian. The systematic repression of politics, the stability of the media, the persecution and eradication of alleged "enemies of the people," limitations on religious practice, and the forcible reconstruction of society through measures like forced collectivization are the main topics of these complaints. Mass detentions, ethnic repression, and the use of forced labor in state-run camps have all been associated with these practices in several historical instances, indicating the lack of political pluralism and the concentration of power in the governing party (Heywood, 2021).

A good example of this direct state control of the media has manifested in section 39 subsection 2 of Nigeria's 1999 Constitution that states that —ownership of the electronic media: radio and television shall be by special license from the president, and staffing shall be controlled by government agents. These types of media stations, within the context of authoritarian powers in Nigeria, have been used to attain the goals of the incumbent leaders, although allowances are still given to private investors to own, establish, and operate media outlets

3.3 Development Media Theory

The development media theory by McQuail's (1987) looks at how the media backs an established government and its efforts to advance socioeconomic development. The limitations of conventional Western normative theories, such as the authoritarian, libertarian, and social responsibility models, which were criticized for failing to take into account the structural, economic, and political realities of post-colonial and developing societies, gave rise to development media theory. It argues that until a nation is well-established and its economic development is well underway, the media should support governments in implementing their plans rather than criticizing them. As the name implies, the hypothesis has to do with media in third-world nations (Onyejelem and Aonover (2024b).

According to media theory, when government development goals conflict with press activity, the state has the right to utilize censorship instruments to interfere with media operations in the overall benefit of development. The media should focus on emerging nations that are politically, geographically, and culturally close. The idea that the media should actively and supportively contribute to national development, especially in developing societies, is highlighted by development media theory. The theory contends that, even if it necessitates some restrictions on media freedom, local culture, national cohesion, and socioeconomic advancement should be given top priority in media practice and content. Development media theory maintains that, in contrast to libertarian viewpoints that prioritize complete press freedom, media autonomy may be curtailed when required to protect group interests and expedite economic and social progress (McQuail, 2015).

At its core, the theory assigns the media a supportive and instrumental role in nation-building. Media institutions are expected to align with government development policies and contribute positively to initiatives in areas such as health, education, literacy, and economic growth. Media freedom, within this framework, is viewed as conditional rather than absolute; restrictions may be justified to prevent content that could undermine development efforts, threaten national cohesion, or incite social instability. As such, collective societal goals are prioritized over individual expressive rights (Christians et al., 2019; Vitalis et al., 2025).

Development media theory also stresses national integration and cultural promotion. The media are encouraged to foster unity by promoting indigenous languages, cultural creativity, and shared national values. In addition, the theory advocates stronger information exchange among developing nations, emphasizing cooperation and solidarity through news flows and communication links between countries facing similar developmental challenges, rather than reliance on Western-dominated media systems (McQuail, 2015).

Within this context, the media are conceptualized as agents of change. They are expected to disseminate democratic ideals, encourage innovation, facilitate social adaptation, and mobilize citizens toward collective development goals, informing and educating the public about national development objectives, motivating citizen participation in development programs, facilitating individual social mobility, and stimulating demand for new ideas, skills, and consumer practices essential for modernization.

Media efforts that actively promote national development goals rather than merely functioning under free-market principles are another real-world illustration of Development Media Theory. This includes health efforts in Nigeria and other developing nations that use radio broadcasts and posters to encourage immunization drives, literacy-improving educational television shows, and news coverage that emphasizes local culture, agriculture, and community development. Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials, films that highlight national projects, and state-sponsored news coverage that supports national development goals and unity are important instruments. In contrast to Western libertarian media approaches that place a higher priority on market-driven content and unrestrained press, these instances demonstrate the theory's emphasis on using the media as a tool for socioeconomic advancement and nation-building.

By foregrounding nation-building and modernization, the theory provides a normative framework that links mass communication directly to socio-economic transformation and the construction of strong national identities (Christians et al., 2019).

3.4 Democratic Participant Theory

According to Denis McQuail's Democratic Participant Media Theory, everyday people have direct access to and control over communication processes in a decentralized, pluralistic, and participatory media system. The theory, which has its roots in democratic ideals, places a strong emphasis on people's active engagement in media production and content. It contends that meaningful participation enhances democracy by enabling people and communities to voice their opinions, discuss issues, and represent regional values and interests. The media should prioritize meeting the wants and goals of its viewers before catering to powerful political or financial interests.

The theory strongly opposes media monopolies, excessive privatization, and bureaucratic control within public media institutions, as these structures limit participation and diversity of expression. Instead, McQuail promotes small-scale, community-based, and non-institutional media that encourage horizontal, two-way communication between senders and receivers. Within this framework, audiences are not passive consumers but active contributors who possess the right to relevant information, to be heard, and to be represented fairly in media content. Media messages, therefore, should remain free from political and bureaucratic interference in order to sustain an inclusive and democratic public sphere.

By promoting numerous local and regional media outlets that represent various socioeconomic groups and cultural identities, Democratic Participant Media Theory places a high priority on decentralization and plurality. In stark contrast to centralized, commercial media systems, the theory aims to establish a media environment that is really democratic—of the people, by the people, and for the people—by promoting interactive feedback, discourse, and community involvement (McQuail, 2015).

Democratic Participant Media Theory's tenets may be seen in Nigerian practices such as public engagement through local media platforms, media involvement in national development projects, and the use of community radio to encourage grassroots participation. However, there are difficulties when there are security risks or national emergencies since more government control over the media may hinder audience-centered media practices and participatory communication (Yar'Adua et al., 2023).

IV. Conclusion

By outlining how the media should function rather than just explaining how it actually does, normative theories of the press offer a fundamental lens through which to view the role of the media in society. The understanding that media are intricately linked to their social, political, and cultural settings unites various perspectives, ranging from authoritarian and libertarian to social responsibility, Soviet-communist, development, and democratic-participant theories. They are tools that both form and are shaped by institutional structures, power dynamics, and societal ideals rather than being neutral players.

Despite their historical influence, classic Western-centric frameworks need to be adapted to new realities, such as digital media, participatory communication, and the pluralistic nature of modern society, as researchers like McQuail have shown through their critical contributions. Democratic Participant Theory and Development Media Theory, for example, emphasize how media can serve nation-building, citizen empowerment, and grassroots engagement, particularly in developing countries, rather than operating purely under market-driven or libertarian principles.

In relation to communication theory, the study of normative media frameworks underscores that media systems must be evaluated not only for efficiency or profitability but also for their social responsibility, ethical conduct, and democratic function. Normative theories provide evaluative criteria to assess media performance against moral, cultural, and political expectations, emphasizing that communication is both a societal process and a tool for shaping social change.

Thus, the ongoing relevance of normative theories lies in their ability to guide media policy, practice, and ethics in a rapidly evolving global and digital media environment, ensuring that communication serves the public interest, democracy, and social development (McQuail, 2015; Christians et al., 2020).

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